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Placing Eliot as a Child Narrator in the Short Story “Mrs. Sen’s” by Jhumpa Lahiri

Dr. Shraddha
Assistant Professor of English,
Swami Karpatri Ji Maharaj Government P.G. College, Raniganj.

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Abstract:

In analyzing the short story “Mrs. Sen” from the collection *Interpreter for Maladies* by Jhumpa Lahiri we as readers can focus on the technique of including child narrators for giving a fresh and honest perspective to the whole story line of an immigrant who had trouble in assimilating in the US. This perspective is valuable in its own right and belongs in the tradition of diasporic or postcolonial storytelling. Through the perspective of Eliot, an eleven year-old-American boy, who becomes somewhat like Mrs. Sen, the title character in the novel, the reader sees a different kind of narrative emerging in the story.

Keywords: alienation, child narrator, food, saris, fish, spices.

Mrs. Sen’s is one of the narratives of the award winning collection of short stories *Interpreter of Maladies*, by Jhumpa Lahiri (1999 Lahiri has used child point of view by introducing child narrators like Lillia and Eliot in the stories “When Mr. Pirzada Came to Dine” and in “Mrs. Sen” respectively in her short story collection. Conceivably, Lahiri tries to give an objective and unbiased picture of diasporic people present in America, through the child narrators. Dickens in particular had

the knack for assuming the child’s perspectives in his novels like *David Copperfield* and *Great Expectations*. Though in Dickensian novels we find Victorian sentiments and pathos but Lahiri has perhaps employed child narrators because as a matter of fact child narrators relates the facts differently than as an adult and child’s focal points or interests differ from that of grown-ups. For instance, “Mrs. Sen” is one of the narratives of the award-winning collection of short-stories *Interpreter of Maladies* in which Eliot an eleven year boy comes to Mrs. Sen to spend time with her as his mother is working and couldn’t find babysitter better than Eliot.

At Mrs. Sen’s house he observes that her apartment was quite warm and radiators continuously made noises with over heat. Eliot learns the habit of removing his sneakers in Mrs. Sen’s doorway. Moreover, Eliot took deep interest in seeing Mrs. Sen as she chopped things seated on newspapers on the living room floor. Eliot very carefully observes the blade that curved like a prow of a ‘Viking ship’. She would split things in half, and then quarters speedily producing florets, cubes, slices and shreds. She could peel a potato in seconds. Lahiri has shown in detail the household chores performed by Mrs. Sen with utmost sincerity through the eyes of Eliot. Eliot also felt that she was scared to keep the blade for cutting vegetables near Eliot. She would warn Eliot repeatedly to keep distance from her while she was surrounded by all the vegetables like spinach, carrots, cauliflower and cabbages.

Eliot keenly observes the blade from India and the story related to the blade which Mrs. Sen tells him about her days in Calcutta where people gathered on festive occasions with their own blades and would chop something or the other for celebration the whole night. She missed the noise and the chatter in her own

apartment provided by the university. In America in her flat, she felt surprised by the silence around her. Eliot also notices the loneliness and sense of trauma in Mrs. Sen's personality when she would say that nobody would come to rescue her if something wrong goes with her in the apartment. Eliot understood that when Mrs. Sen said "home" she meant India not the apartment in which she lived and chopped vegetables. Lahiri has gone into detail to observe the lifestyle of Mrs. Sen and all her marks of marriage like wearing vermilion in the parting of her. As Eliot observes she smelled of mothballs and cumin. Eliot also thought that Mrs. Sen had cut her scalp or if something had bitten her hair-line. Mrs. Sen even explained to Eliot that she wears red dot over her eyebrows as a symbol of marriage for the rest of her life. The boy then compares the red dot with wedding ring which is a mark of marriage in his culture in America. Only an innocent child could imagine such little details which are though very irrelevant for an aged person but very relevant in the sense of making a narration worth reading for the readers and the writer who is writing and weaving the short story.

Eliot also understood that Mrs. Sen would remove all her chopped items, the blade and onion skin and the waste part of meat and fish before Eliot's mother arrives to bring Eliot back with her after her work. In fact, Eliot helped her in crushing all the peels and seeds and skins inside them. Eliot always felt surprised that for only two people Mrs. Sen would prepare so much without any guests at home.

Furthermore, Eliot compared his mother's method of preparing food which usually consisted of a glass of wine and bread and cheese at night for the dinner. At the dinner table she would only ask how had spent his whole day and later she moved to the deck to smoke a cigarette leaving Eliot to remove the leftovers. The

dichotomy between Mrs. Sen and Eliot’s mother (or his entire mother culture) does suggest a binary structure. The child character Eliot, a young member of his younger generation like a grown up person sees the cross cultural and in-between condition of the diasporic lives.

At his young age Eliot is able to recognize Mrs. Sen longing and despair just by watching her, but he never opens up before his mother. He does so by not telling his observations thus starting to become more loyal to Mrs. Sen and disloyal to his own mother. Here, we can assume that the in-betweenness and the cultural conflict seems to disappear in the increasingly manner. The little boy becomes one with the thought and emotions of Mrs. Sen. The whole American culture undergo transformation through Eliot’s acceptance of Mrs. Sen as a mother figure unconsciously.

Furthermore, Eliot remembers Mrs. Sen waiting for his school bus at the bus stop to pick him up. Eliot always sensed that Mrs. Sen had been waiting for sometime as if she had not met him in years. Eliot notices all the minute details of her sari and attire. She wore navy blue sunglasses a little too big for her face. Her sari a different pattern she wore each day fluttered below the hem of a checkered all weather coats. As they walked back from the bus stop she produced a sandwich bag from her pocket, and offered Eliot the peeled wedges of an orange, or slightly salted peanuts, which she had already shelled.

Lahiri also elaborated on the driving practice which Mrs. Sen undertook. She practised in a toffee-colored sedan with vinyl seats. There was an AM radio with chrome buttons and on the ledge over the back seat, a box of Kleenax and an icecream scraper. Mrs. Sen told Eliot she didn’t feel right leaving him alone in the

apartment but Eliot already knew that it was due to her own loneliness that she wanted him around her all the time possible. Eliot could sense that Mrs. Sen feels afraid of being alone as she has expressed her anxiety many a number of times before her. Here, also in the car she desired to drive in his company. She dreaded the roar of the ignition, and placed her hands over her ears to block out the sound as she pressed her slippers feet to the gas, revving the engine.

Eliot could feel that Mrs. Sen had fear or mental disturbances due to her loneliness in America and her inability to learn new things made her behave awkwardly in many situations. She was waiting for her licence, unconsciously she desired to get freedom after receiving her licence and even she asked him that licence would give her chance to drive back to Calcutta her 'Home'. She always referred to Calcutta as her home. She even roughly calculated the speed and time hours it would take to go back to Calcutta.

“Could I drive all the way to Calcutta? How long would that take, Eliot? Ten thousand miles, at fifty miles per hour?” (119)

Eliot could not do the maths in his head. Eliot was not sure that Mrs. Sen would pass the test before receiving her licence. Eliot looks sometimes Mrs. Sen's unconscious mind through him she needs assurance and reassurance. She remains in a conflict compounded with many doubt and fears all sometimes hovering over her brain repeatedly and in Eliot she required that support which would keep all her worries at bay.

Eliot understood very well that Mrs. Sen felt distracted. She would stop the car without warning just to listen something on the radio or to stare at something. She

behaved as if she was a prisoner inside the car just to learn car for the sake of learning and only with a desire to fly away from her present state of mind. Eliot also feels that Mrs. Sen felt uncomfortable because in India the driver sat on the right side not on the left.

As Eliot thinks to himself, two things, made Mrs. Sen happy. One was the arrival of a letter from her family. It was her custom to check the mailbox after driving practice. She would unlock the box, but she would ask Eliot to reach inside, telling him what to look for, and then she would cover her eyes with her hands while he shuffled the bills and magazines that came in Mrs. Sen’s name. At first Eliot found Mrs. Sen’s anxiety incomprehensible; his mother has P.O. Box in town, and she collected mail so infrequently that once their electricity was cut off for three days. Eliot also observes with his keen eyes that once an aerogram arrived, grainy to the touch, crammed with stamps showing a bald man at a spinning wheel, and blackened by post marks. Eliot took it out and showed it to Mrs. Sen. This letter gave the news of a birth of a baby girl to her sister. Eliot notices all these little day to day details. Eliot even notices how she informs Mr. Sen regarding the news of her niece’s birth and in a voice which almost deafened little Eliot’s ears.

Once, Mrs. Sen asked Eliot whether he missed his mother while he lives with her all the day. Eliot felt surprised since he didn’t know at all whether his mother misses him at all or not. His mother was a divorced lady who hardly cared for anything but Eliot’s safety was her only concern. She never cared leaving Eliot alone at the dining table, without finishing the dinner, she often went to upstairs for smoking cigarette. The other thing which made Mrs. Sen happy was fish from the seaside. She loved the whole fish.

Eliot also recollects that once Mrs. Sen flung open the drawers in her bedroom filled with saris of every imaginable texture and shade, brocaded with gold and silver threads. Some were transparent, tissue thin, others as thick as drapes, with tassels knotted along the edges. In the closet they were on hangers: in the drawers they were folded flat, or in rolls. She tossed the saris one by one from the drawers, and then pried several from their hangers. Most strikingly Eliot notices that the room was filled with the smell of the mothballs kept in the fold of the saris. The smell of the mothball seems quite strange to Eliot.

Lahiri through her craft of writing has evoked all the sense imagery in Eliot. He sees Mrs. Sen's outfits like coats and saris. He was surprised by Mrs. Sen's culinary skills. Her love for fish and the variety of food which she prepared from time to time throughout the day. Mrs. Sen's house smelled of cumin and other spices. Her touch as motherly as he could never expect in a feminine personality even in his own dominant culture. Moreover, all the advice which Mrs. Sen would give to this little eleven year old boy "...when you are a man your life will be in places you cannot know now. She counted on her fingers...". (131) He could hear Mrs. Sen like a teacher as well. Though Eliot finds her talk obscure and absurd at times but she completes his whole personality as a boy who was later ready to live all alone in his own house no matter he was okay or not. Mrs. Sen was beyond everything for the little boy Eliot.

Mrs. Sen also informs Eliot that people at home asks for her pictures. "They think I live the life of a queen, Eliot...They think I press buttons and the house is clean. They think I live in a palace." (125) Lahiri has shown very softly and in detail about the mental agony of Mrs. Sen which only a little boy Eliot could understand.

Sometimes it even surprises the readers that how so much information is stored in the mind of a little boy who is foreign to an Indian lady and her way of life. Nevertheless, this is all the writers’ perspective to bring in thorough detail the life of an Indian immigrant who went to the U.S. in early 1960’s and 1970’s.

In the later part of the story as Eliot sees Mrs. Sen neglects her driving practice. Once she visits with Eliot and Mr. Sen shops for eating and while coming back to home Mrs. Sen had hit the car. Though Eliot was lucky to come out without a scratch when Eliot’s mother arrived at Sen’s place, Mr.Sen told her the details of the accident and offered a cheque reimbursing November’s payment. As he wrote out the cheque he apologised on behalf of Mrs. Sen. So for Eliot it came the last afternoon with Mrs. Sen or any babysitter. The child narrators give very honest and straight pictures of people’s life around them. The story of Eliot is not different. We see him growing up with Mrs. Sen. His narration is simple, soft and clear. The story took up events after events in plain words. He had described Mrs. Eliot agony, pain and moments of relief very keenly and with truth like features in the story. We could sense the flow of images over and over with all the details like a motion picture of some serious and poignant movie which portrayed the amateur experience of an Indian woman in the back nineties who took the charge of household in the alien land but mentally and physically drained herself just to keep them occupied. On the other side we could also sense through Eliot’s eyes the routine of hard pressed Mr. Sen who works at the University with very little time for the homesick wife. Had he been able to give time and space to Mrs.Sen she might have not gone into the trouble seeking help in a small child like Eliot.

Eliot’s mother gave him a key which he wore on a string around his neck and nobody accompanied him in the afternoons post school hours. His mother called

him on the phone and consoled him that he was a big boy who could manage things on his own. The dichotomy between Mrs. Sen and Eliot's mother (or his entire mother culture") does suggest a binary structure. Within that structure, however, the narrative contains a muddling and mixing that becomes possible thanks to the child character Eliot, member of a younger generation even though Eliot's mother remains unchanged throughout the story.

Another point which emerges is that who is lonely. Whether it is Mrs. Sen so lonely or Eliot too is equally lonely. If we look deeply into it not only Eliot but his own culture is lonely. This aspect as it comes out, the new reading emerges and brings in a counter narrative. This underlying narrative symbolises the empowerment of the minority culture in the context of mutual contact between the minority and the majority culture. Adaptation and assimilation in these contact spaces do not restrict change to the minority culture. Mrs. Sen's strength is displayed in transforming another human being and in other words symbolically the dominant culture. The majority culture and its representatives, although the second generation, undergo changes as well.

Lahiri has softly yet powerfully employed this child narrator and carefully crafted Mrs. Sen's character in the story which depicts the ultimately failed search for identity and home. And it could be read as Mrs. Sen's failing to adapt to the American ways of living, symbolized here by her fear of driving and the resulting catastrophe. Indeed, Lahiri is a modern realist. Though her story is cohesive and simple but contains rich abundance of food narration which also includes descriptions of culinary items and processes.

In addition to the above mentioned aspects food culture and preparation in the story is solely not presented through Mrs. Sen perception but also by the placement of the child narrator Eliot at the center of the narrative which shows his experience of his home culture and the Indian food culture. This new experience creates a new space, a new hybrid and fluid sense of community that has the potential to subvert the dominant American culture.

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